

Photocatalytic study of cubic and mixed phase of nano cadmium sulphide

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Abstract : Cadmium sulphide in nano form is prepared by solid state method using cadmium chloride and sodium sulphide at two different grinding periods, say, 1/2 h and 3 h designated as (CdS-a) and (CdS-b) respectively. The as-prepared products are characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), UV-Vis spectroscopy (UV-Vis), Scanning electron microscope (SEM) and Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). CdS-a, exist in cubic form and with increasing grinding period, there is a phase transformation from cubic phase (CdS-a) to mixed (cubic+hexagonal) phase (CdS-b). The compounds are subjected to photocatalytic decolorization study with methyl orange (MO) and rhodamine B (RB) under UV and sun light. Based on the study, it has been observed that under both UV and sunlight, mixed phase CdS-b shows greater photocatalytic efficiency against MO than RB.

Keywords : Nano CdS, phase transformation, photocatalyst, methyl orange.

Introduction

Textile and other dye industries, by their effluents, pose a greater threat to existing water bodies causing extensive environmental degradation. Several technologies like anaerobic reduction^{1,2}, flocculation³, adsorption⁴, ultra filtration⁵, reverse osmosis⁶ and extraction⁷, have been adopted towards the same. However, these techniques are able to transfer the pollutant only from one form to another form⁸ and therefore in recent years, different types of advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) are developed such as ultraviolet light, hydrogen peroxide, ozonation, Fenton, photocatalysis and combination of these techniques^{9,10} for water treatment. The efficient and economical photocatalytic technique depends on the solar spectra that fall in the visible region^{11,12}. Towards achieving improved photocatalytic efficiency, more attention has recently been focused on nanotechnology to develop a wide range of novel photocatalytic nanomaterials. CdS, a well known semiconductor material, is one among the few known nanomaterials studied extensively till recently¹³.

As part of our ongoing efforts towards the preparation of nano CdS, a simpler solid state method has been adopted. We have varied the ground periods (1/2 h and 3

h) and obtained two different forms of CdS. In our earlier report, we have discussed in detail on cubic phase (CdS-a)¹⁴ and its photocatalytic applications. In the current study, we have focused on mixed phase nano CdS (CdS-b) and its photocatalytic efficiency towards both the dyes, MO and RB.

Experimental

Materials :

CdCl₂ (99.5%), utilized as it was received from Thomas Baker. Na₂S (99%) and methyl orange were purchased from SD Fine Chemicals. Distilled water was used for sample preparations.

Methods :

CdS compounds are prepared based on our earlier report¹⁴. Briefly, CdCl₂ (3 mmole) and Na₂S (3 mmole) were taken in equimolar ratios and ground uniformly at different durations of time, say, 1/2 h and 3 h. The product was thoroughly washed by 100 ml distilled water with continuous stirring for 30 min. The CdS obtained as orange colored precipitate was separated and washed by distilled water and ensured for complete removal of NaCl.

Photocatalytic study :

25 mg of sample was dissolved in 50 ml aqueous so-

lution of MO/RB (0.5 mg/50 ml) and sonicated for 30 min. 2 ml of aliquots were taken at specified time intervals and monitored by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 464 nm and 554 nm for MO and RB respectively.

Characterization :

The compounds were characterized by powder X-ray Diffraction (XRD) using Bruker D8 Advance, Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) using FEI Quanta FEG 200 and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) using JEOL JEM 2100 to find out the surface morphology and particle size.

Results and discussion

X-Ray analysis/Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy :

Based on a few reports on the preparation of CdS, it has been observed that higher temperature favors phase transformation with the band gap value of 2.42 eV¹⁵⁻¹⁸. To start with, in our current work, we have increased the grinding period so as to achieve phase changes. This work will be continued further by varying the annealing temperatures. Fig. 1(a) shows XRD pattern of CdS obtained by increasing grinding period up to 3 h coded as CdS-b. It reveals the existence of mixed (cubic + hexagonal) showing the predominant peak (111) for cubic coexisting with the evolving peak (101) for hexagonal observed at 28.21° (JCPDS-80-0019). Cubic phase is represented as

“c” and hexagonal phase represented as “H”.

The optical absorbance for CdS compounds ranges between 490–495 nm depends on photon energy to estimate the band gap (E_g), for crystalline and amorphous materials.

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = B(h\nu - E_g)$$

where B = energy independent constant, n = nature of transition (for direct transitions, $n = 2$ and indirect transitions, $n = 1/2$).

As CdS has directly allowed transitions and so n is taken as 2. A plot between $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ gives a linear portion and the extrapolation of the same gives E_g value and was found to be 2.24 eV for CdS-b (Fig. 1 (b)).

SEM/TEM analysis :

Fig. 2(a) and (b) show SEM and TEM images of CdS-b respectively. The fine particles of nano CdS-b, appears agglomerated and show rough surface morphology. The HRTEM image of CdS-b represents lesser dispersion of nanoparticles with particles in the range of 20–30 nm size.

Photocatalytic studies :

The de-colorization of MO and RB solution by CdS-b with respect to time as monitored by measuring their absorbance at 464 nm and 554 nm respectively is shown in

Fig. 1. (a) X-Ray diffraction patterns of CdS-b mixed phase and (b) $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy curve of CdS-b.

Fig. 2. (a) SEM image and (b) TEM image of CdS-b.

Fig. 3. UV-Visible spectra of MO and RB solution with respect to time (a) CdS-b + MO (sunlight), (b) CdS-b + MO (UV), (c) CdS-b + RB (sunlight), (d) CdS-b + UV light (RB) and (e) photocatalytic degradation study of CdS-b on MO/RB (UV and sunlight).

Fig. 3(a-d). The degradation was calculated from the ratio (C/C_0) of absorbance of dye in which C represents the absorbance shown by dye solution after specified time period and C_0 is the absorbance noted at zero time, once the homogeneous solution prepared shown in Fig. 3(e). Based on the results obtained, it has been confirmed that mixed phase CdS-b shows a satisfactory dye decolorizing efficiency for MO under UV and sun light with 89.09% and 70.87% respectively. But, it shows lesser effect for RB under UV and sun light with 68.13% and 60.44% respectively. The varying efficiency of CdS-b towards MO/RB may be attributed to various factors like size, phase, surface morphology of CdS and also due to the nature of dyes.

Conclusions

Solid state method was used to develop CdS compounds. CdS prepared at 3 h (CdS-b) grinding period shows mixed phase whereas the reported cubic phase CdS (CdS-a) is formed at lesser grinding period. This proves that increasing grinding period favors phase evolution towards hexagonal phase and the work to achieve pure hexagonal phase CdS is underway. Further, we have observed that CdS-b shows greater photocatalytic efficiency for MO than RB, under UV and sunlight.

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